

OPPORTUNITIES OF THE EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER IN THE UPDATED INFORMATION-EDUCATION ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *The unification of several modern institutions in an educational cluster is based on the interaction based on the use of the main organizational forms of different levels of education, departmental affiliation and inter-network cooperation of educational institutions of different directions. The article mentions that the association of clusters based on mutual network influence has the potential to increase educational resources, didactic opportunities, attract well-known experts, increase the scope of innovative influence and the potential of research activities.*

Keywords: *cluster, industry, region, business, collaboration, innovation, resource, intuition, intelligence, creativity.*

Today, the most important condition for solving the planned educational tasks in terms of improving the general and professional education system, increasing the quality of specialist training and adapting it to society's requirements is the creation and formation of multi-level regional education systems in the form of clusters aimed at solving problems in this field. The development of educational clusters covering the entire period of personality formation is one of the urgent directions of adaptation of the educational sector to external market conditions, which allows to identify the principles of organizational economic impact, methods and modern approaches of educational services market management, interaction of resources, collective interests and cooperation of all participants of the educational process. is considered The most important reason for the emergence of clusters in the world economy is the limitation of the scope of technological changes in the industry and increased competition. An enterprise cannot enter the market alone, it must merge with another.

L.A. Aleksandrova, Kh.Kh.Bekaldiev, I.G.Zakharova and others were interested in cluster approach and cluster policy issues, which led to the introduction of cluster ideas into the field of education [1].

It is related to the need to connect educational cluster development programs, fundamental developments and modern information technology design systems, methods of their development, as well as training and professional retraining of personnel necessary for the implementation of these programs within one function or area. The employer providing educational services, that is, the customer, defines the educational cluster as a source of knowledge, skills and competencies oriented to multifaceted practice, which allows to determine the directions of priority financial investments. The educational cluster works as a single system, the main task of which is to organize a multi-level system of training of professional personnel.

M. Enright developed the theory of regional clusters. The author examines sectoral differences in competitiveness within countries and competitive advantage across geographic scales. According to M. Enright, competitive advantages are formed at the regional level, where at the national level, the aspects of historical development of the regions, the different appearance of business, the implementation of production and the diversity of education play a key role.

According to the author, regional clusters are the main object of implementation of the state's cluster policy [2].

The unification of several modern educational institutions in an educational cluster is based on the interaction based on the use of the main organizational forms of different levels of education, departmental affiliation and mutual network cooperation of educational institutions of different directions. Also, the association of clusters based on mutual network influence allows to increase educational resources, didactic opportunities, attract well-known specialists, increase the scope of innovative influence and the potential of research activities. From the point of view of innovation, educational clusters are growth points where the activities of various specialized educational institutions are concentrated [3].

The state education system sets the task of achieving a new quality of education at the expense of the planned educational results. The final result of education, including general and higher professional education, is the formation of a person who can adapt to socio-economic changes in society, is comprehensively developed and can find his place in the present era. Development of these qualities is the main goal of modern educational results [4].

Until recently, the system of higher professional education trained highly qualified personnel based on the traditional content of education and existing methods, organizational forms and tools of the educational process, but today they need to be changed, because they can no longer ensure the achievement of new educational results.

According to the research results of psychologists and pedagogues on the structure and characteristics of the personality of learners, V.I. Andreev identifies the following personal characteristics that should form the basis of new educational results:

- motivational qualities. A modern school student should possess the following: constant interest in the process of continuous learning and independent learning and self-development, the desire to learn about the world, art and culture. Such a student should be able to engage in strong work activities, have a positive attitude in school and in society.

- spiritual and moral qualities. A modern student should be morally educated, that is, he should be an honest, fair, humane, intelligent, humble, open, flexible, compassionate, kind, self-developing person.

- physical qualities. A modern student should be strong, healthy, active in sports, that is, ready for physical self-development and self-improvement.

- intellectual qualities. A modern student should be a visual (spatial) and critical thinker, creative, knowledgeable, intellectual and logical thinker, creative, intelligent and sensitive.

- business qualities. A modern student should be responsible, hardworking, quick, business-minded, planned, disciplined, risk-taker, able to bring any work to its logical conclusion as an individual.

- organizational and willpower qualities. A modern student should be a self-demanding, purposeful, organized, self-critical, strong-willed person.

- social qualities. A modern student should be a person who has a humanitarian outlook, active citizenship and social principles, can understand other people, and has self-respect.

- universal adjectives. A modern student should be able to work mentally and physically, have economic, environmental, legal, political culture, communication and behavioral culture, and aesthetic culture [5].

A.B. Vorontsov defines the following main results of education and upbringing: science (academic) results: basic competencies or a set of universal educational activities, assimilation of social experience or personal development results. The author pays special attention to the results of mutual education. These are the main results and serve the integral educational performance of the student who goes through educational directions and educational stages [6].

In the conditions of the need to transition to new organizational forms, the need to build an educational process in the environment of a new educational cluster, it is possible to monitor the changes in the content of students' activities in these separate components, based on such analyzes, it was possible to justify the approaches and principles of the methodological system of education.

Gnostic component. In the use of new organizational forms in the educational process, the gnostic structural component is necessary to regulate the student's activity taking into account the psychological-pedagogical and didactic possibilities of new forms of education. That is, new organizational forms of education for the student, taking into account the psychological-pedagogical and age characteristics of the students, directional teaching, lectures, seminars, networking, telecommunication projects, case technologies; intra-group relations, network communication, determination of inter-group and interpersonal relations of students in planned education; in order to use and generalize the effective organizational forms, methods and tools of education in their professional and pedagogical activities, to analyze the experience of leading teachers, as well as to use teachers' pedagogical teams, forums, conversations; additional knowledge is needed to analyze the effectiveness of educational organization forms at school.

The next component of the student's activity is the design component, which is necessary for replacement in the changing conditions of information technology tools. These factors indicate that the main component that should be developed in the student is the design component. It is necessary to develop the design of the educational process by using innovative organizational forms based on ICT tools in the updated information-educational environment at the school. That is, it is necessary to analyze the modern goals of the new type of education system, to choose the content of the subject to be studied, to be able to build the most important ways of the subject to be taught, to be able to choose innovative organizational forms and tools of education based on modern methods, ICT, to improve or create training programs and training manuals.

The importance of pedagogical design increases when using telecommunication projects aimed at developing students' independent activities at school. Students complete a learning project (in groups, pairs, or individually) for a specified period of time as directed by the teacher.

According to P.P. Podlasyy, the task of a modern teacher is to have the ability to manage the educational and educational process of an educational institution. Clarifying the tasks of the teacher, the author uses the concept of "pedagogical project", which can be any completed work - a lesson, an extracurricular activity, learning a new topic or section, etc. [7].

Thus, a modern teacher must acquire the following skills within this component: specialized education at school, modular education, planning of distance education process; designing training, that is, changing the existing educational material based on the use of new organizational forms of education on the basis of ICT tools in accordance with the specific didactic tasks and goals of the lesson. Such a teacher should be able to design the methodical equipment of training sessions, choose rational organizational forms, new methods and educational tools based on ICT tools; Must be able to plan student activities and pedagogical management structure using Internet network resources, networking, forums, chats, e-mail consultations; He should be able to

plan the new information-educational environment of the school, taking into account the didactic possibilities of modern organizational forms of education based on ICT tools.

Communicative component. In the use of new organizational forms in the educational process, new knowledge and skills are necessary for the teacher within the framework of this component, that is: with groups of students, as well as with leaders, colleagues, parents, government representatives, business partners, network tools: pedagogical teams, forums, chats, electronic establishment of targeted pedagogical cooperation using mail; finding the right approach and relationship with different colleagues and students in pedagogical cooperation with different educational network societies; attract students' attention, if necessary, restore relations with students in the group, apply an individual approach to them in project education, laboratory work, case technology assignments.

In addition, the teacher should develop the following: the readiness and ability of students for self-development and personal development, their educational and purposeful cognitive activities, the system of important social and interpersonal relationships, the essence of values, legal awareness, the ability to set goals and make life plans, multicultural formation of motivation to realize individuality in society.

Individual results should be reflected in:

- the formation of tolerant behavior and consciousness of a person in a multicultural world, the ability and readiness to communicate with other people, to achieve mutual understanding, to find common goals and to cooperate in order to achieve them;

- the formation of the skills of effective cooperation with peers, younger and older children, adults in the field of education, scientific-research, social-useful, educational-innovative and other activities;

- lifelong learning and self-education; readiness and ability for a conscious attitude in continuous education as a condition for successful professional and social activity.

Significant changes in the conditions of introduction of modern organizational forms of education in the updated information-educational environment are included in the organizational structure of the teacher's work. A modern teacher: must be an organizer of distance, full-time, home education using new organizational forms of education based on ICT tools; when introducing specialized education in a general education school, it is necessary to organize the educational process based on individual educational directions and individual educational plans of students using new organizational forms of education based on ICT tools.

In order to conduct training sessions, such a teacher should be able to justify the purpose, tasks and content of the subject being studied, to be able to determine the educational tasks that need to be solved, to choose the appropriate educational methods to solve them, to be able to determine innovative organizational forms of ICT tools by methods, to choose educational tools by forms should receive, that is, be the organizer of the educational process at school. During the course of the training, such a teacher: organizes a network of students to discuss the most relevant issues of the subject being studied; using case technologies - the ability to creatively solve the studied problem, analyze the educational situation and make appropriate decisions in problematic situations; design activities for the development of students' knowledge, research, design activities, and at the same time, the creation of an educational product designed to solve a scientific, technical or other educational problem; thematic teleconference with students of different schools; must be able to arrange individual and group consultations, including email consultations.

At the same time, due to the introduction of credit-module education in the upper classes of the general education school, the teacher can divide the educational material into several modules, justify the tasks, purpose and content of each module; providing access to different modules depending on whether the student passed or failed the previous module (in the form of test-module training) or whether the student scored or failed to score the points required to pass the module (in the form of test-rating). When organizing the educational process, the teacher should understand what students are being evaluated on, what they are getting points for, that is, the teacher should create a new evaluation system for students, for example, a 100-point system. Thus, it can be noted that the teacher's duties do not end with the transfer of information to students, he should be the organizer of students' acquisition of new knowledge, the initiator of creative and educational activities.

Expert component. A modern teacher should be an expert in the field of applying new organizational forms in the educational process, as well as in studying the educational possibilities of modern organizational forms of improving the quality of education.

Thus, the opportunities of the educational cluster in the updated information-educational environment are determined by the formation of a person who is fully developed, ready to work independently and has the ability, skills and qualifications to adapt to rapidly changing professional and social conditions.

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